

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25

***Marinobacter aquaticus* sp. nov., a moderately halophilic bacterium from a solar
saltern**

María José León, Cristina Sánchez-Porro and Antonio Ventosa*

Department of Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of
Sevilla, 41012 Sevilla, Spain

Running title: *Marinobacter aquaticus* sp. nov.

Subject category: New Taxa - Proteobacteria

*Corresponding author. Tel: +34 954556765; fax: +34 954628162.

E-mail address: ventosa@us.es.

The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number for the 16S rRNA gene sequence of
strain M6-53^T is LT714149.

26 A moderately halophilic bacterium designated as strain M6-53^T was isolated from
27 water of a pond from a marine saltern located in Huelva, South-West Spain. The
28 strain was Gram-stain-negative, strictly aerobic, motile slightly curved rod, able to
29 grow in media containing 5-25 % (w/v) NaCl (optimal growth at 10 % [w/v]), at
30 temperatures from 20 to 40 °C (optimally at 37 °C) and at pH 7-9 (optimally at pH
31 7.0). Phylogenetic analysis based on 16S rRNA gene sequences placed the new
32 isolate within the genus *Marinobacter*, being the most closely related species
33 *Marinobacter persicus* IBRC-M 10445^T (98.5% similarity), *Marinobacter*
34 *oulmenensis* Set74^T (97.2%) and *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus* ATCC
35 49840^T (97.1%). The major fatty acids present in strain M6-53^T are C_{18:1} ω_{9c}
36 (29.5%), C_{16:0} (26.7%), C_{12:0} 3-OH (15.1%), C_{18:0} (10.2%) and C_{16:1} ω_{9c} (9.6%). The
37 G+C content of the genomic DNA for this strain was determined to be 56.4 mol%.
38 The DNA-DNA hybridization between strain M6-53^T and *Marinobacter persicus*
39 CECT 7991^T, *Marinobacter oulmenensis* CECT 7499^T and *Marinobacter*
40 *hydrocarbonoclasticus* DSM 50418^T were 8, 41 and 38 %, respectively. These values
41 are lower than 70 % threshold and showed that the new isolate constituted a
42 different species within the genus *Marinobacter*. Phylogenetic analysis based on the
43 16S rRNA gene sequence and the phenotypic, genotypic and chemotaxonomic
44 features of this new isolate support the placement of strain M6-53^T as a new
45 species of the genus *Marinobacter*, for which we propose the name *Marinobacter*
46 *aquaticus* sp. nov., with strain M6-53^T (= CECT 9228^T = LMG 30006^T) as the type
47 strain.

48

49 Most microbiological studies in hypersaline environments have been carried out on
50 aquatic habitats, mainly saline lakes and salterns. Salterns used for the commercial
51 production of the common salt constitute excellent models for studies focused on the
52 biodiversity and ecology of microorganisms in these environments. They usually have
53 multi-ponds systems, offering a wide range of salinities from that of seawater
54 concentration to salt saturation [1-3]. Culture-based studies conducted on several
55 salterns have led us to the isolation in the last years of numerous halophilic
56 microorganisms, including representatives of the genus *Marinobacter*. The genus
57 *Marinobacter* was first proposed by Gauthier *et al.* [4], it belongs to the family
58 *Alteromonadaceae*, within the order *Alteromonadales* in the phylum *Proteobacteria*.
59 This genus includes a large number of species that have been isolated from a variety of
60 marine and hypersaline environments, comprising at the time of writing 41 species with
61 validly published names [5]. The genus *Marinobacter* includes aerobic, Gram-stain-
62 negative, rod-shaped and motile species [6].

63 Recently, we isolated a strain designated as M6-53^T from the water of a pond of a
64 saltern located in Isla Cristina, Huelva, in South-Spain. Partial 16S rRNA gene
65 sequence data suggested that strain M6-53^T was closely related to the genus
66 *Marinobacter* and could constitute a novel species of this genus. In the present study we
67 have carried out a polyphasic characterization with the aim of defining the exact
68 taxonomic position of this new strain, including a detailed determination of the
69 phenotypic and genotypic features and a phylogenetic analysis based on the 16S rRNA
70 gene sequence.

71

72 Strain M6-53^T was isolated during a sampling carried out in October 2011 from a water
73 pond of Isla Cristina saltern, Spain. The isolation medium was modified from HM

74 medium, previously described by Ventosa *et al.* [7], and contained (g l⁻¹): NaCl, 117;
75 MgCl₂·6H₂O, 19.5; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 30.5; CaCl₂, 0.5; KCl, 3; NaHCO₃, 0.1; NaBr, 0.35;
76 yeast extract, 0.5; sodium pyruvate, 1.1, solidified with 1.8 % agar (BD). The pH of this
77 medium was adjusted to pH 7.5 with 1 M KOH. Strain M6-53^T was isolated by plating
78 0.1 ml of the water sample on the medium after incubation for one month under aerobic
79 conditions at 37 °C. The strain was subsequently purified three times by plating on the
80 same medium. The strain was routinely grown in SMM medium, previously described
81 by León *et al.* [8] at 37 °C. The composition of this medium was the following (g l⁻¹):
82 NaCl, 46.8; MgCl₂·6H₂O, 19.5; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 30.5; CaCl₂, 0.5; KCl, 3.0; NaHCO₃, 0.1;
83 NaBr, 0.35; casein digest, 5.0 and sodium pyruvate, 1.1. When necessary the medium
84 was solidified with 1.8 % agar. The pH was adjusted to 7.5 with 1 M KOH. The strain
85 M6-53^T was maintained at -80 °C in SMM medium containing 30 % (v/v) glycerol. The
86 type strains *Marinobacter persicus* CECT 7991^T, *Marinobacter oulmenensis* CECT
87 7499^T and *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus* DSM 50418^T were used as reference
88 strains for comparative purposes in our study. They were cultivated under the same
89 conditions as for strain M6-53^T.

90 For the determination of the cellular morphology and motility an exponential liquid
91 culture of strain M6-53^T was examined by phase-contrast microscopy (Olympus CX41).
92 Strain M6-53^T was a motile slightly curved rod with a size of 0.5 µm wide by 1.0-2.5
93 µm long, Gram-stain-negative and occurred singly but some chains were observed. The
94 morphology of colonies, their size and pigmentation were determined on SMM solid
95 medium after 4 days of incubation at 37 °C. Colonies were circular, entire, white-cream
96 and approximately 0.5-1.0 mm after 4 days of incubation at 37 °C. The optimal and
97 growth range at different NaCl concentrations (0, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 %, w/v)
98 were determined using SMM medium at pH 7.5, according to León *et al.* [9]. To

99 determine the pH range and the optimal pH to grow for the isolate M6-53^T we cultivated
100 the strain at pH 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 7.5, 8.0, 9.0 and 10.0, adjusted with the addition of the
101 appropriate buffering capacity to each medium [10]. The optimal and range of
102 temperature were determined by incubating the strain at temperatures of 5-45 °C at
103 intervals of 5 °C. Strain M6-53^T is a moderately halophilic bacterium able to grow in
104 media containing 5 to 25 % (w/v) NaCl and at pH 6.5 to 9.0 showing an optimal growth
105 at 10 % (w/v) NaCl and at pH 7.0. It was not able to grow in the absence of NaCl. The
106 temperature range for growth was 20-40 °C with an optimal growth at 37 °C. All
107 biochemical tests were carried out in SMM medium at 37 °C, unless otherwise stated.
108 Catalase activity was defined by bubble production in 3 % (v/v) H₂O₂ solution. Oxidase
109 activity was examined with 1 % (v/v) tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine [11]. In order to
110 determine the presence of growth of strain M6-53^T under anaerobic conditions cells
111 were incubated in SMM medium in an anaerobic jar using Anaerogen (Oxoid) to create
112 an anaerobic atmosphere and using an anaerobic indicator (Oxoid). Hydrolysis of
113 casein, DNA, gelatin, starch, Tween 80 and aesculin, nitrate and nitrite reduction,
114 Voges-Proskauer and methyl red tests, oxidation-fermentation from carbohydrates,
115 production of indole and phosphatase and urease activities were determined as
116 described by Cowan & Steel [12]. Citrate utilization was determined on Simmons'
117 citrate medium supplemented with 10 % (w/v) salts. Strain M6-53^T was catalase and
118 oxidase positive. Hydrolysis of Tween 80 and DNA were positive but negative for
119 aesculin, starch and gelatine. Indole and H₂S were not produced. Simmons' citrate was
120 negative. Nitrate and nitrite were not reduced. Phosphatase was positive. Methyl red,
121 Voges-Proskauer and urease tests were negative. Acid was not produced from D-
122 arabinose, sucrose, D-fructose, D-mannose, glycerol, D-amygdaline L-citruline, D-
123 ethionine, inuline, lactose, D-melezitose, D-ribose, raffinose, sorbitol or xylitol. For

124 determining the range of substrates used as carbon and energy sources or as carbon,
125 nitrogen and energy sources, the classical medium of Koser [13] as modified by
126 Ventosa *et al.* [7] was used. Solutions of the different substrates were sterilized by
127 filtration and added to media to give a final concentration of 1 g l⁻¹, except for
128 carbohydrates, which were used at 2 g l⁻¹. For the determination of the utilization of
129 amino acids as carbon, nitrogen and energy source the basal medium was prepared
130 without KNO₃ and (NH₄)₂HPO₄. The following compounds were not utilized by the
131 strain M6-53^T as sole carbon and energy source: D-arabinose, L-raffinose, ribose,
132 lactose, maltose, glycerol, D-mannitol, D-sorbitol, xylitol, L-citruline, benzoate,
133 fumarate, hippurate, naphthalene or dulcitol. Strain M6-53^T is able to use pyruvate as
134 carbon and energy source, or L-phenylalanine, L-ornithine and L-glutamine as carbon,
135 nitrogen and energy source. Other phenotypic features are shown on the species
136 description and Table 1.

137 Genomic DNA from strain M6-53^T was extracted using the method described by
138 Marmur [14]. The 16S rRNA gene was amplified by PCR with the forward primer
139 16F27 and the reverse primer 16R1488 [15]. The almost-complete 16S rRNA gene
140 sequence of strain M6-53^T (1,455 bp) was deposited in GenBank and used for initial
141 BLAST searches. The identification of phylogenetic neighbours and calculation of
142 pairwise 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity were achieved using the EzTaxon-e server
143 [16] and the ARB software package [17]. The 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis
144 showed that strain M6-53^T is a member of the genus *Marinobacter*. The 16S rRNA gene
145 sequence similarities between strain M6-53^T and the most closely related species of
146 *Marinobacter*, *Marinobacter persicus* IBRC-M 10445^T, *Marinobacter oulmenensis*
147 Set74^T and *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus* ATCC 49840^T were 98.5 %, 97.2 %
148 and 97.1 %, respectively. Other related species were *Marinobacter pelagius* HS225^T

149 (96.8 %), *Marinobacter salarius* R9SW1^T (96.8 %) and other members of the genus
150 *Marinobacter* (with similarities equal or lower than 96.5 %). The 16S rRNA gene
151 sequence of strain M6-53^T was aligned with the published sequences of the closely
152 related bacteria and the alignment was confirmed and checked against both primary and
153 secondary structures of the 16S rRNA molecule using the alignment tool of the ARB
154 software package. Phylogenetic trees were constructed using three different methods:
155 maximum-likelihood [18], maximum-parsimony [19] and neighbour-joining [20],
156 algorithms integrated in the ARB software for phylogenetic inference. Bootstrap test
157 was performed by calculating 1000 replicate trees [21]. The phylogenetic analysis based
158 on the maximum-likelihood algorithm revealed that strain M6-53^T clustered with
159 *Marinobacter* species, being the most closely related species *Marinobacter persicus*
160 M9B^T. The phylogenetic position of strain M6-53^T was also observed in trees calculated
161 using the neighbour-joining and maximum-parsimony algorithms (Fig. 1).

162 The G+C content of the genomic DNA of strain M6-53^T was determined from the mid-
163 point value (T_m) of the thermal denaturation profile [22] using the equation of Owen &
164 Hill [23], obtained with a Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis Lambda 20 spectrophotometer at 260
165 nm equipped with a PTP-1 peltier system programmed with an increasing of
166 temperature of 1 °C/min. The DNA G+C content of strain M6-53^T was estimated to be
167 56.4 mol%. This value is very close to the values reported for the most closely related
168 species *M. persicus* M9B^T (58.6 mol%) [24], *M. oulmenensis* Set74^T (57.4 mol%) [25]
169 and *M. hydrocarbonoclasticus* SP.17^T (52.7 mol%) [4].

170 DNA-DNA hybridization (DDH) studies were performed by the competition procedure
171 of the membrane filter method [26]. The hybridization temperature was 54.4 °C, within
172 the limit of validity for the filter method [27]. The percentage of hybridization was
173 calculated according to Johnson [26]. The experiments were performed in triplicate. The

174 percentages of DNA–DNA hybridization between strain M6-53^T and *M. persicus* CECT
175 7991^T, *M. oulmenensis* CECT 7499^T and *M. hydrocarbonoclasticus* DSM 50418^T were
176 8, 41 and 38 %, respectively. These DDH relatedness values were lower than 70 %
177 threshold, currently accepted as the cut-off value for species delineation [28, 29], and
178 revealed that the new strain M6-53^T constitutes a novel species of the genus
179 *Marinobacter*.

180 Fatty acids analysis was performed using the MIDI Microbial Identification System
181 [30]. This analysis was carried out by the CECT (Spanish Collection of Type Cultures,
182 Valencia, Spain) using gas chromatography (Agilent 6850) and a standardized protocol
183 according to the MIDI Sherlock system [31]. Cellular fatty acid composition of strain
184 M6-53^T was determined in cells cultivated on MH medium at 37 °C for 48 hours, the
185 same culture conditions used for the fatty acids analysis of the most closely related
186 species *M. persicus* M9B^T. The major fatty acids determined for strain M6-53^T were
187 C_{18:1} ω_{9c} (29.5 % of total fatty acids), C_{16:0} (26.7 %), C_{12:0} 3-OH (15.1 %), C_{18:0} (10.2
188 %) and C_{16:1} ω_{9c} (9.6 %). These fatty acids are also predominant in the most closely
189 related species and other members of the genus *Marinobacter*; however some
190 differences were found in the proportions of these fatty acids (Table 2). Additionally,
191 the fatty acid C_{19:1} ω_{6c}, a major component in *M. persicus* CECT 7991^T was present in
192 minor amount (lower than 0.5 %) in strain M6-53^T.

193 Results obtained from the taxonomic characterization of strain M6-53^T, based on a
194 phylogenetic, phenotypic, genotypic and chemotaxonomic study indicated that this
195 isolate could be classified as a new species of the genus *Marinobacter*, for which we
196 propose the name *Marinobacter aquaticus* sp. nov.

197

198 **Description of *Marinobacter aquaticus* sp. nov.**

199 *Marinobacter aquaticus* (a.qua'ti.cus L. masc. adj. *aquaticus*, living or found in the
200 water, aquatic).

201 Cells are Gram-stain-negative, motile aerobic slightly curved rods, with 0.5 x 1.0-2.5
202 μm , non-endospore-forming. Colonies on SMM medium are circular, white-cream and
203 0.5-1.0 mm after 4-5 days of incubation at 37 °C. Catalase and oxidase positive.
204 Moderately halophilic. No growth occurs in media without NaCl. It grows from 5 to 25
205 % (w/v) NaCl with an optimal growth at 10 % (w/v) NaCl. Grows at pH values on the
206 range 6.5-9.0 and at 20-40 °C; showing an optimal growth at pH 7.0 and at 37 °C.
207 Hydrolysis of Tween 80 and DNA are positive. Aesculin, gelatin and starch are not
208 hydrolysed. Indole and H₂S are not produced. Simmons' citrate is negative. Indole and
209 H₂S are not produced. Phosphatase is positive, but methyl red, Voges-Proskauer and
210 urease tests are negative. The following compounds are not used as sole carbon and
211 energy source: D-arabinose, D-xylose, L-raffinose, ribose, lactose, maltose, glycerol,
212 erythritol, D-mannitol, D-sorbitol, xylitol, L-citruline, benzoate, fumarate, malate,
213 valerate, acetate, succinate, formate, hippurate, naphthalene, dulcitol, butanol, and
214 propanol. Pyruvate is used as sole carbon and energy source. L-phenylalanine, L-
215 ornithine and L-glutamine are used as sole carbon, nitrogen and energy source.
216 However L-serine, L-alanine, D-histidine, L-valine, ethionine, L-glycine, D,L-lysine, L-
217 cysteine, L-methionine and L-isoleucine are not used.

218 The major fatty acids are C_{18:1} ω 9c, C_{16:0}, C_{12:0} 3-OH, C_{18:0} and C_{16:1} ω 9c. The DNA
219 G+C content of the type strain is 56.4 mol%.

220 The type strain is M6-53^T (= CECT 9228^T = LMG 30006^T), isolated from the water of a
221 pond of Isla Cristina saltern, located in Huelva, Spain.

222

223 **Acknowledgements**

224 M. J. León was recipient of a postdoctoral fellowship from the Junta de Andalucía,
225 Spain. We thank Salud Rodríguez and Ilknur Aksoy for their assistance in the
226 laboratory.

227

228 **Funding information**

229 This work was supported by a grant from the Spanish Ministerio de Economía y
230 Competitividad (CGL2013-46941-P) with European funds (FEDER).

231

232 **Conflict of interest**

233 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

234

235 **Ethical statement**

236 No experimental work with animals or human has been carried out in this study.

237

238

239 **References**

- 240 **1. Ventosa A, Fernández AB, León MJ, Sánchez-Porro C, Rodríguez-Valera**
241 **F.** The Santa Pola saltern as a model for studying the microbiota of hypersaline
242 environments. *Extremophiles* 2014;18:811-824.
- 243 **2. Oren A.** Halophilic microbial communities and their environments. *Curr Opin*
244 *Biotechnol* 2015;33C:119-124.

- 245 **3. Ventosa A, de la Haba RR, Sánchez-Porro C, Papke RT.** Microbial diversity
246 of hypersaline environments: A metagenomic approach. *Curr Opin Microbiol*
247 2015;25:80-87.
- 248 **4. Gauthier MJ, Lafay B, Christen R, Fernandez L, Acquaviva M et al.**
249 *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus* gen. nov., sp. nov., a new, extremely
250 halotolerant, hydrocarbondegrading marine bacterium. *Int J Syst Bacteriol*
251 1992;42:568–576.
- 252 **5. Parte AC.** LPSN-list of prokaryotic names with standing in nomenclature.
253 *Nucleic Acids Res* 2014;42:613-616.
- 254 **6. Cui Z, Gao W, Xu G, Luan X, Li Q, Yin X, Huang D, Zheng L. (2016).**
255 *Marinobacter aromaticivorans* sp. nov., a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon-
256 degrading bacterium isolated from sea sediment. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol*
257 2016;66:353-359.
- 258 **7. Ventosa A, Quesada E, Rodriguez-Valera F, Ruiz-Berraquero F, Ramos-**
259 **Cormenzana A.** Numerical taxonomy of moderately halophilic Gram-negative
260 rods. *J Gen Microbiol* 1982;128:1959-1968.
- 261 **8. León MJ, Vera-Gargallo B, Sánchez-Porro C, Ventosa A.** *Spiribacter roseus*
262 sp. nov., a moderately halophilic species of the genus *Spiribacter* from salterns.
263 *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2016;66:4218-4224.
- 264 **9. León MJ, Martínez-Checa F, Ventosa A, Sánchez-Porro C.** *Idiomarina*
265 *aquatica* sp. nov., a moderately halophilic bacterium isolated from Spanish
266 salterns. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol*, 2015;65:4595-4600.
- 267 **10. Sánchez-Porro C, de la Haba RR, Soto-Ramírez N, Márquez MC,**
268 **Montalvo-Rodríguez R et al.** Description of *Kushneria aurantia* gen. nov., sp.
269 nov., a novel member of the family *Halomonadaceae*, and a proposal for

270 reclassification of *Halomonas marisflavi* as *Kushneria marisflavi* comb. nov., of
271 *Halomonas indalinina* as *Kushneria indalinina* comb. nov. and of *Halomonas*
272 *avicenniae* as *Kushneria avicenniae* comb. nov. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol*
273 2009;59:397-405.

274 **11. Kovacs N.** Identification of *Pseudomonas pyocyanea* by the oxidase reaction.
275 *Nature* 1956;29:703.

276 **12. Cowan ST, Steel KJ.** *Manual for the Identification of Medical Bacteria.*
277 London: Cambridge University Press; 1965.

278 **13. Koser SA.** Utilization of the salts of organic acids by the colon-aerogenes group.
279 *J Bacteriol* 1923;8:493-520.

280 **14. Marmur J.** A procedure for the isolation of deoxyribonucleic acid from
281 microorganisms. *J Mol Biol* 1961;3:208-218.

282 **15. Márquez MC, Carrasco IJ, Xue Y, Ma Y, Cowan DA et al.** *Aquisalibacillus*
283 *elongatus* gen. nov., sp. nov., a moderately halophilic bacterium of the family
284 *Bacillaceae* isolated from a saline lake. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2008;58:1922-
285 1926.

286 **16. Yoon SH, Ha SM, Kwon S, Lim J, Kim Y et al.** Introducing EzBioCloud: A
287 taxonomically united database of 16S rRNA and whole genome assemblies. *Int*
288 *J Syst Evol Microbiol.* 2017. (in press).

289 **17. Ludwig W, Strunk O, Westram R, Richter L, Meier H. et al.** ARB: A
290 software environment for sequence data. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2004;32:1363-1371.

291 **18. Felsenstein J.** Evolutionary trees from DNA sequences: A maximum likelihood
292 approach. *J Mol Evol* 1981;17:368-376.

293 **19. Fitch WM.** Toward defining the course of evolution: Minimum change for a
294 specific tree topology. *Syst Biology* 1971;20:406-416.

- 295 **20. Saitou N, Nei M.** The neighbor-joining method: A new method for
296 reconstructing phylogenetic trees. *Mol Biol and Evol* 1987;4:406-425.
- 297 **21. Felsenstein J.** Confidence limits on phylogenies: An approach using the
298 bootstrap. *Evolution* 1985;39:783-791.
- 299 **22. Marmur J, Doty P.** Determination of the base composition of deoxyribonucleic
300 acid from its thermal denaturation temperature. *J Mol Biol* 1962;5:109-118.
- 301 **23. Owen RJ, Hill LR.** The estimation of base compositions, base pairing and
302 genome size of bacterial deoxyribonucleic acids. In *Identification Methods for*
303 *Microbiologists*, 2nd ed; F. A. Skinner & D. W. Lovelock (ed). London:
304 Academic Press; 1979. pp 217-296.
- 305 **24. Bagheri M, Amoozegar M, Didari M, Makhdoumi-Kakhki A, Schumann P**
306 *et al.* (2013). *Marinobacter persicus* sp. nov., a moderately halophilic
307 bacterium from a saline lake in Iran. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 2013;104:47-
308 54.
- 309 **25. Kharroub K, Aguilera M, Jiménez-Pranteda ML, González-Paredes A,**
310 **Ramos-Cormenzana A et al.** *Marinobacter oulmenensis* sp. nov., a moderately
311 halophilic bacterium isolated from brine of a salt concentrator. *Int J Syst Evol*
312 *Microbiol* 2011;61:2210-2214.
- 313 **26. Johnson JL.** Similarity analysis of DNAs. In: *Methods for General and*
314 *Molecular Bacteriology*; Edited by P. Gerhardt, R. G. E. Murray, W. A. Wood
315 & N. R. Krieg. Washington, D.C: American Society for Microbiology; 1994.
316 pp. 655-681.
- 317 **27. De Ley J, Tijtgat R.** Evaluation of membrane filter methods for DNA-DNA
318 hybridization. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 1970;36:461-474.

- 319 **28. Stackebrandt E, Goebel BM.** Taxonomic note: a place for DNA-DNA
320 reassociation and 16S rRNA sequence analysis in the present species definition
321 in bacteriology. *Int J Syst Bacteriol* 1994;44:846-849.
- 322 **29. Stackebrandt E, Fredericksen W, Garrity GM, Grimont PAD, Kämpfer P.**
323 Report of the ad hoc committee for the re-evaluation of the species definition in
324 bacteriology. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2002;52:1043-1047.
- 325 **30. MIDI.** *Sherlock Microbial Identification System Operating Manual, version 6.1.*
326 Newark, DE: MIDI Inc; 2008.
- 327 **31. Sasser M.** *Identification of bacteria by gas chromatography of cellular fatty*
328 *acids, MIDI Technical Note 101.* Newark: DE: MIDI Inc; 1990.
- 329 **32. Márquez MC, Ventosa A.** *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus* Gauthier *et al.*
330 1992 and *Marinobacter aquaeolei* Nguyen *et al.* 1999 are heterotypic synonyms.
331 *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2005;55:1349–1351.
- 332

333 **Legend to figure**

334

335 **Fig. 1.** Maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree based on the complete 16S rRNA gene
336 sequences showing the relationships between strain M6-53^T and the most closely related
337 species of the genus *Marinobacter*. Sequence accession numbers are shown in
338 parentheses. Bootstrap values higher than 70 % are shown above the branch. *Hahella*
339 *chejuensis* 96CJ10356^T (GenBank accession no. CP000155) was used as outgroup. The
340 GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number of each sequence is shown in parentheses.
341 Filled circles indicate that the corresponding nodes were also obtained in the trees
342 generated with the maximum-parsimony and neighbour-joining algorithms. Bar, 0.01
343 nucleotide changes per position.

344

345 **Table 1.** Differential characteristics of strains M6-53^T and the most closely related
 346 species of the genus *Marinobacter*. Strains: 1, M6-53^T; 2, *Marinobacter persicus* CECT
 347 7991^T; 3, *Marinobacter oulmenensis* CECT 7499^T and 4, *Marinobacter*
 348 *hydrocarbonoclasticus* DSM 50418^T. +, Positive; -, negative; ND, not determined.

349

Characteristic	1	2	3	4
Cell morphology	Slightly curved rods	Rods	Rods	Rods
Colony pigmentation	White-cream	Orange to yellow	Cream	White
Cell size (µm)	0.5 x 1.0-2.5	0.5 x 4.0-7.0 ^a	0.3-0.5 x 1.6-3.0 ^b	0.3-0.6 x 2.0-3.0 ^c
NaCl range (% w/v)	5-25	5-20 ^a	1-15 ^b	0.5-20 ^a
NaCl optimum (% w/v)	10	7.5-10 ^a	5-7.5 ^b	ND
Temperature range for growth (°C)	20-40	25-45 ^a	30-45 ^b	10-45 ^c
Temperature optimum (°C)	37	35 ^a	37-40 ^b	32 ^c
pH range	6.5-9.0	6.0-8.0 ^a	5.5-9.0 ^b	6.0-9.5 ^a
pH optimum	7.0	7.0 ^a	6.5-7.0 ^b	7.0-7.5 ^a
Hydrolysis of				
DNA	+	-	+	-
Nitrate reduction	-	-	-	+
Nitrite reduction	-	-	-	+
Simmons' citrate	-	-	+	+
Utilization of:				
Xylitol	-	+	+	ND
D-mannitol	-	+	+	ND
Dulcitol	-	+	+	ND
L-alanine	-	+	+	ND
L-isoleucine	-	+	+	ND

D, L-lysine	-	+	+	ND 350
Fumarate	-	+	+	+
Propanol	-	+	+	351 +
DNA G+C content (mol%)	56.4	58.6 ^a	57.4 ^b	52.7 52

353

354 ^a Data from Bagheri *et al.* [24]; ^b Data from Kharroub *et al.* [25]; ^c Data from Gauthier
355 *et al.* [4].

356

357 **Table 2.** Cellular fatty acids composition of strain M6-53^T and the most closely related
 358 species of the genus *Marinobacter*. Values are percentages of the total cellular fatty
 359 acids. Strains: 1, strain M6-53^T; 2, *Marinobacter persicus* M9B^T; 3, *Marinobacter*
 360 *oulmenensis* Set74^T and 4, *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus* DSM 8798^T. -, Values
 361 lower than 0.5 % or not detected. Data were obtained in this study unless otherwise
 362 indicated. All strains were grown under the same growth conditions, as indicated in the
 363 methods.

Fatty acid	1	2 ^a	3 ^b	4 ^c
C _{10:0}	3.7	0.9	-	1.0
C _{12:0}	2.1	2.8	6.2	6.5
C _{12:0} 3-OH	15.1	8.7	9.4	10.3
C _{14:0}	0.8	2.6	-	2.8
iso C _{14:0}	-	1.5	-	-
C _{15:0}	-	-	-	1.7
C _{16:0}	26.7	28.1	29.0	30.3
iso C _{16:0}	0.3	2.7	-	-
C _{16:1} ω _{9c}	9.6	10.1	8.6	9.4
C _{16:1} ω _{7c}	-	-	-	5.6
C _{17:0} cyclo	-	-	-	2.4
C _{17:0}	0.9	1.7	-	3.5
C _{17:1} ω _{8c}	-	0.3	-	2.8
C _{18:0}	10.2	6.3	7.2	1.8
C _{18:1} ω _{9c}	29.5	12.6	19.6	19.6
C _{18:1} ω _{7c}	-	-	-	0.5
C _{19:0} cyclo ω _{8c}	-	-	-	-
C _{19:1} ω _{6c}	-	19.3	-	-

364

365 ^a Data from this study and Bagheri *et al.* [24]; ^b Data from Kharroub *et al.* [25]; ^c Data
 366 from Márquez *et al.* [32].

Figure 1

